

A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE CONSIDERATION OF DAMAGE ENTITIES IN 3D WOVEN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: This paper addresses the microstructural features of multilayer woven composite materials and how they collectively contribute to the overall deformation response. Due to the complexity of perceived interplay amongst damage parameters within the composite material, an energy framework is used as a basis to rationalise the manifestation of these parameters within a deformation response scenario. These parameters are quantified in general terms of damage tensors and are shown to resemble energy-type functions. The discussion in this paper is centred around geometrical features of fibre configurations in multilayer woven glass fibre composite panels with a lattice of uncrimped warp and weft yarns supported by through-thickness weft binders.

KEYWORDS: damage entities, energy, representative volume element (RVE), thermodynamics, continuum mechanics, woven composites, deformation response

INTRODUCTION

The study of damage in composite structures has attracted some interest of late due to emerging technologies used in experimental and computational techniques. This increased sophistication in obtaining credible experimental and computational data has allowed the development of analytical techniques that, for the first time, can incorporate these new physical and computational data. The trend in recent years has been to gain an insight into the progressive mechanics of failure rather than coming up with some universal failure criterion in the study of the mechanical properties of composite structures.

This paper attempts to describe the damage progression, in the warp and weft directions, of 3-D woven polymer matrix composites when statically loaded in the tensile mode. The main design feature-based variables are the binder configurations and comparison in strength between the warp and the weft directions; the binders are only present in the weft direction. A typical binder-architecture design used in the study reported in [1] is shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1 Orthogonal through-thickness binder (idealised schematic)

This paper is an extension of Talreja's work [3] on damage mechanics in composite materials to 3-dimensional woven composite structures. A theoretical energy framework is introduced to utilise energy-related damage entities as observed from micrographs of damage zones in these structures. The intent here is to attempt to initiate novel experimental techniques that can be based on sound theoretical and computational developments in the field of damage mechanics.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

General

The view taken in this paper is that trying to predict observed macromechanical behaviour from essentially micromechanical features is extremely difficult and that the results are predicated on assumptions that are in many instances, very hard to justify. What will be attempted here however, is to build up an argument by identifying and quantifying parameters thought to be players in the overall process of composite failures. As a stance taken by several others [3, 4, 5], and that adopted in this paper, it is essential not to pursue absolute agreement between theory and experiment but rather to emphasise general trends and identify consistencies. The reasons of taking this route of analysis evolved out of the realisation that the ever changing physical and geometric entities involved in the failure process of polymer matrix composite components **cannot** be modelled and measured accurately in its entirety. The challenge is however, to identify and model significant parameters thought to be responsible for macromechanical behaviour, particularly that of static deformation and failure modes. The discussion [6, 7, 8, 10] currently evolves around whether a continuum mechanics, thermodynamic or a combination of both models is appropriate for providing a sound theoretical basis for understanding the deformation process in 3D woven composite structures. A discussion on this subject is given below.

The concept of a unit cell or Representative Volume Element (RVE) is introduced here and a typical element is essentially a 3-dimensional version of Fig. 1. This is used to represent yarn and binder configurations as well as a cell that would have polymer matrix composite microstructural entities such as voids, interfaces and cracks is not unlike the RVE in the work of Nemat-Nasser and Hori [5] and Talreja [3, 4]. Using the concept of a damage entity as

defined by Talreja in [3], it is an individually identifiable change in the microstructural constitution of a solid which is brought about by an internal energy dissipative mechanism. Examples in the context of the present study include voids, cracks, debonds and interfacial slip. A vectorial representation of damage is chosen so that both magnitude and orientation of the damage is defined. A conceptual damage entity modified by Talreja [3], defines a damage entity d_{ij} as:

$$d_{ij} = \int_S a_i n_j dS \quad (1)$$

where S is the surface area of the damage entity; a_i and n_j are ‘damage-influencing’ and normal vectors associated with the damage entity as shown in Fig. 2. If a_i is taken as some function of displacement, then if a_i is zero, d_{ij} fails to qualify as a damage entity. Another definition, a damage mode, [2] is a collective reference to a subset of damage entities which, on account of their geometrical features and the local driving forces, evolve in a similar fashion. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 2, assuming there are n distinct damage modes in the RVE of volume V , denoted by $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, n$, a damage tensor is defined for each mode as:

$$D_{ij}^\alpha = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where k_α is the number of damage entities in the α th mode.

Fig. 2: A Damage entity: yet to be physically quantified

Equation (2) is then used as a field variable using the Coleman-Gurtin [6] theory of thermomechanical response, to get stiffness-damage relationships as shown by Talreja *et al* [3, 7]. This essentially showed a form of virgin or undamaged property degradation as shown in Equation (3) below for the case of cross-ply laminates with intralaminar cracks:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_1 &= E_1^0 - f(C, \nu) \\
E_2 &= E_2^0 - f(C, \nu) \\
\nu_{12} &= \nu_{12}^0 - f(C, E_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Where E^0 and ν^0 is the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio respectively in the undamaged state and C is a combined representation of material constants and geometrical entities.

3-Dimensional Woven Composites

As the damage entity as defined in Equation (2) above is not feature or mechanism-specific, it can be applied to any RVE and all suspected damage entities can be incorporated in it. As the RVE for the 3-D composite structure considered here involves both geometric and inherent damage entities, the actual RVE for deformation analysis should strictly be the superpositioning of Fig. 1 (3D version [1]) and Fig. 2. Also, as mentioned above, the theoretical thrust here is **not** to identify **all** the damage and geometrical entities responsible for deformation but to highlight prominent players in this process such as voids, fibre breaks, debond areas and fibre-matrix interface slip.

Consider the damage entity in Equation (1), d_{ij} , to be a form of dissipative (unrecoverable) work done by a damage entity such as a growing crack, then,

$$d_{ij} = \int_S a_i n_j dS \Rightarrow \left. \frac{\partial w}{\partial a} \right|_{Microcrack} \tag{4}$$

where $\partial w / \partial a$ is the local elastic energy release rate; w is the energy and a is the crack length.

Similarly, if d_{ij} represents some sort of work done by the damage entity such as a debond, then,

$$d_{ij} = \int_S a_i n_j dS \Rightarrow \int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \tag{5}$$

where $\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij}$ is the strain energy density, dW/dV [2].

John *et al* [1] showed that the damage tensor for a 3-D woven composite structure should incorporate not only the inherent damage entities such as that represented by Equations (4) and (5), but also that from the woven yarn and binder configurations. Therefore, Equation (2) would decompose to:

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \left| \text{Inherent Damage} + \sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \left| \text{Woven Geometry} \right. \right. \right) \tag{6}$$

Evidence of damage from the ‘Woven Geometry’ Component of Equation (6) is reported by John *et al* in [1].

DISCUSSION ON AN ENERGY-BASED CONSTITUTIVE FRAMEWORK

The need to quantify the damage variables above emanates from the desire to place these evolving entities into a framework around which physical arguments can be made. The intent here is to predict a material response to external forces rather than emerge with some sort of failure criterion for 3D woven composite components. Gurney [10] argues that continuum mechanics cannot cater for stress-induced phase changes. Thermodynamic considerations by Gurney [10], Talreja [3] and Colman *et. al* [5], have all resulted in considerations of entities other than damage such as entropy, heat flux vectors and 'Helmholz' free energies; all of which are phenomenologically difficult to measure and adapt to 3D composite structures. As a result, the following analysis is undertaken.

Assuming a RVE, α , shown in Fig. 2, is an isothermal, quasi-static and macro-elastic system, the energy transformations within it are both reversible and irreversible, albeit on a microscale. Ignoring any phase change due to an evolving damage entity such as a disbond or an initiating crack, the external work, at time $t = 0$ (pre-damage evolution), W can be expressed as:

$$dW_o = d\Lambda_o + RdA \tag{7}$$

where Λ is reversible work, R is the fracture toughness, A is the ‘new crack area’ (in this case, meant to collectively represent voids, potential disbonds sites, friction and other irreversible energy phenomena) and subscript o refers to a the pre-mechanical induced damage state. Equation (7) is that used by Gurney [10] to describe elastic cracking and using this as a simplistic model to incorporate damage entities as described in Equations (4) to (6). Elucidating further, $d\Lambda$, will represent the reversible elastic within the RVE (such as locked in strain energy during the component manufacture), which is expected to dominate the minor irreversible energy changes represented by $R dA$.

Fig. 3: Schematic of suspected mechanics responsible for binder-inflicted damage

At time $t > 0$ (after the onset of damage induced by mechanical deformation), $d\Lambda$ begins to transform to irreversible energy dissipation such as the damage from the binder causing

microcracks in the yarn tows as reported in [1] and illustrated in Fig. 3. Therefore Equation (7) becomes:

$$dW_i = d\Lambda_r + \sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Int} + \sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Ext} \quad (8)$$

where,

$$d\Lambda_r = d\Lambda_o - \sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Int} \quad (9)$$

and the total summation of irreversible energies within the RVE is,

$$\sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Total} = \sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Int} + \sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Ext} \quad (10)$$

where t_i is the time during which irreversible new energy dissipations have occurred as a direct result of a diminished $d\Lambda_r$ due to internal strain energy conversions from reversible ($d\Lambda$) energy to irreversible ($\sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA$) energy. The $\sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Ext}$ component is the irreversible energy transformations from disbonds, matrix cracking and so on, directly attributable to the external load. From the results displayed in [1], it is postulated that if the damage entities are identified and suitably quantified as energy terms similar to the strain energy definition [1] in Equation (5), it can be equated to $\sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Total}$, i.e.,

$$\sum_{t=0}^{t=t_i} RdA|_{Total} \Rightarrow D_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \Big|_{Inherent\ Damage} + \sum_{k_\alpha} (d_{ij})_{k_\alpha} \Big|_{Woven\ Geometry} \right) \quad (11)$$

CONCLUSION

From the analysis proposed above, it is clear that the challenge is how to quantify the damage entities in Equations (4) - (6) and how these manifest themselves in an energy framework described in Equation (8) - (11). It needs to be recognised that while binders can have a deleterious effect on the composite structure as proposed in Equation (6) and as suggested by John *et. al* in [1], it might have benefits in other ways. It must be stated here that while a thermodynamically-based constitutive framework is probably a more rigorous and thorough approach to understanding micro and meso-phenomena in composite materials, parameters within it remain very difficult to measure. On the other hand, the continuum mechanics approach is also, inherently flawed for quantifying entities with constantly evolving geometrical and physical parameters. The energy approach is suggested as a model to relate phenomena (physical and otherwise) in a deforming body. The challenge remains the proper definition of damage and other entities involved in the deformation response of

3D composite structures and how they can correctly be transformed to energy functions as indicated in Equation (11) .

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